

Collation of cryptographic tool information for DCC protection and validation

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1 General information on digital signatures

Replacement of paper-based calibration certificates by digital counterparts Digital Calibration Certificates (DCCs) is vital for the digital transformation of many European industrial and legal metrology sectors. However, not all members of the European metrology community have access to the knowledge and capabilities needed for the implementation of DCCs. The small collaborative project EMPIR 21SCP01 DCC2GO has addressed this issue by supporting the implementation of DCCs within the European metrology community through the coordinated production and sharing of training material (PTB, 2022). This guideline is part of the information material produced by DCC2GO. The document focuses on aspects of protection and secure submission of DCCs. It comprises different types of mechanisms for securing the content of DCCs such as digital signatures.

1.1 Background

Issuing, transferring, using, and archiving calibration certificates in electronic form brings forward the need of knowing the origin and authenticity of certificates and assurance that data in certificates is complete and unchanged. The set of information that forms a DCC can be signed electronically as we would sign paper documents by hand. Using electronic signature is the broad category of (mathematical) methods for signing a document in electronic form, sometimes called “digital signature” where specific signature technology is implemented.

1.2 Need for digital signing

Choosing the means of electronic signing comes down to capturing and reviewing the requirements of the parties involved in the creation and receiving the calibration certificate. Requirements can vary depending on the use-case, industry branch, legal requirements within a country etc.

The majority of calibration service providers in Europe are ISO/IEC 17025 accredited or follow the requirements of this standard to some extent (ISO/IEC, 2018). The above-mentioned standard does not require signing of certificates directly, but it does require the identification of the person(s) authorising the reports or certificates. The general requirements for the integrity and authenticity of the data and information can be fulfilled by electronically signing documents. In addition, there may also be national requirements specifically ordering certificates to be signed.

1.3 Different types and levels of digital signatures

Depending on the situation and legal requirements for the protection of certificates from manipulation (integrity) and proving the identity of the issuer (authenticity) one of the electronic or digital signature types listed in Table 1 may be applied.

Table 1 Outline of different types of electronic and digital signature

Type	Description	Example
Type 1 (not signed but protected)	The original version of the certificate (electronic file) is stored in a database system that ensures protection of the content from manipulation and long-term authenticity. Comparison of copies of the certificate to the “protected” original version allows checking of integrity.	specific electronic file systems for administration, Write Once - Read Many memory (WORM, 2023)
Type 2 (simple signature)	The electronic document contains an electronic image of a handwritten signature of the authorizing person. In addition, a simple write-protect mechanism is in place, that prevents accidental change of the content of the document.	PDF file with image of signature and write protection within PDF (Adobe, 2023), MS Word file with write-protect
Type 3 (advanced electronic signature)	The certificate is protected by deployment of a cryptographic methods based on a Private-Public-Key methods (PKI, 2023). The customer can verify the signature. The security level is normal. The signature meets the technological requirements established in standards. This type can be further distinguished by that if backgrounds of both the owner of the signature and the issuer of the certificate can be checked.	signed PDF using a PKI certificate from the domain of network and web-service protection (DCC2GO, 2023) or a service provider not qualified under the EU trusted list (Commission, 2023)
Type 4 (qualified signature – eIDAS conform)	Signature with an eIDAS regulation conforming method (eIDAS, 2023). Within Europe, such signed documents, their integrity, and authenticity are legally watertight. The signature meets the technological requirements established in standards. The backgrounds of both the owner of the signature and the issuer of the certificate are checked. Additionally, the signature is given with a means that is deemed suitable (ID-cards, digital IDs, mobile-IDs).	signed document and signing service provider in EU trusted list (“self declared”), e.g., Estonian governmentally backed signing system with .asice file containers (ID, 2023)
Type 5 (non-European signature method)	A signature method with legal acceptance in a non-EU country is used, e.g., a method valid in the US or in the Asian pacific region. This could be relevant for services offered beyond Europe.	for example, a signature applicable to the ESIGN Act in the United States (Wikipedia, 2023)

There are various commercial providers of signing services available worldwide as well as government backed services in some countries (EU Trust Providers list is a good source to find eIDAS compliant providers (eIDAS, 2023) . The signature can be linked to a physical person or to an organisation (legal person), in which case it can be called an electronic seal. Selecting the relevant solution is dependent on the number of signatures per person. However, it is difficult to make a general recommendation as requirements across organisations can vary significantly. In general, the type (and security level) of electronic signatures has to be chosen depending on institution’s internal and national rules, taking in account the usability to customers, cost of implementing the system and possible cost of a single signature (including both time spent for signing and fee for service provider).

Clearly in future there will be cases beyond type 5 with as yet undefined additional functionality. This could include software that supports the individual user groups (or actors) from the calibration community including those from NMI to industrial manufacturer. For example, members of the national, European and/or international quality infrastructure agree on and manage their own tools and infrastructure for trusted and legally secure signatures particularly for certificates in the quality infrastructure. As an example for this, the German body of

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accreditation DAkkS is issuing an electronic seal for use exclusive use by accredited laboratories (DAkkS, 2023). This seal is called 'eAttestation'.

The majority of commercially available services rely on asymmetric encryption and more specifically the Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) principle (PKI, 2023). More information can be found from EMPIR project SmartCom outcome documents (SmartCom, 2021).

1.4 Considerations when moving to digital signing

When choosing a method for electronic signing the following typical questions should be considered:

- Is the signature uniquely and securely linked to the signee?
- Is the signature linked to the data signed there with in such a way that any subsequent Is change in the data is detectable?
- Is there an audit trail with time stamp available?
- In case of EU users is it in compliance with GDPR (REGULATION (EU), 2016) and is data processing made (servers located) inside EU/EEA area (EEA, 2023)?

An organisation may also find some of the following reasons for signing DCC are relevant:

- Need from regulation – digital solution equivalent to hand-written signature
- Signature used as a symbol for quality & trust (part of marketing)
- Need to verify sender and content (as postal trust by paper enveloped) – confirmation that the DCC is from the expected sender, and is the document that was meant to be sent - digital security by signature
- Need to limit who can open the document (as postal secret - only dedicated receiver can receive document) – solution provided by signing tools

2 Overview of two examples of digital signing

2.1 Signing of PDF files

Principle

A PDF/A-3 document is used as a file container including the human-readable part of the certificate (document readable with a PDF viewer) and having attached files (attachment within PDF) providing machine-readable data from calibration. The deployment of a signature restricts the ability of further manipulation or change of the information within the PDF (human readable part). The level of protection depends on the chosen signature service provider.

For protecting the attached machine-readable documents from manipulation (making manipulation visible), the concept from METAS for example is to introduce unique fingerprints (hash values / check sums) for each attached document. At the assembly of the document, the creator uses a standardized method (hash algorithm) to calculate the fingerprint for each attachment. The values of each fingerprint are stored within the PDF part that is protected by

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the signature. The user can apply the same method to calculate the hash values of the attached files. If the values obtained by the user differ from the reference values in the PDF, it is an indicator that data has been manipulated. The values can also be attached in a machine-readable file. The DCC2GO guideline for creating DCCs comprise a simple example for signing a PDF/A-3 file (DCC2GO, 2023). The examples is using a type 3 signature from Table 1.

Security and legal requirements

PDF/A-3 supports different signature types for different legal requirements. These types are

- Simple handwritten electronic image or text with name of the signer(s) at signature filed (type 1) for basic protection of content. After application of the signature, the document is protected from manipulation with basic means applied by PDF creating software.
- Advanced electronic signature (based on PKI certificate with private and public key) for basic check of integrity and authenticity (type 2). After application of the signature, the document is protected from manipulation and users can verify the electronic signature.
- Qualified digital signature (based on PKI and for example eIDAS compatible methods) for legally watertight signature (type 3). After application of the signature, the document is protected from manipulation and users can verify the electronic signature based on a legally highly secure method.

Advantages

- If an organisation is already working with (electronically signed) PDF documents, the transition to the PDF/A-3 file container is easy and existing tools for working with PDF can in many cases be directly used to apply and verify electronic signatures. Thus, it is easy to use for customers, who still depend more on the human readable content.
- Many PDF tools (e.g., Acrobat Reader, Foxit Reader) provide means to create image of hand-written electronic signatures and electronic signatures based on cryptographic certificates (PKI). Thus, additional costs for signing PDF/A-3 could be easier to manage.

Disadvantages

- The digital (cryptographic) protection of the attached machine-readable files needs the workaround with hash values. To verify that the data has not been manipulated, additional software is needed by the creators and users of the calibration data. If automation of verification is required, the transcription of the reference hash values from the PDF to software is not trivial.
- Deployment and validation of qualified digital signatures / seals (as in Table 1, type 4) require additional tools that are typically not part of standard PDF tools. E.g., DocuSign (used for example in VTT Finland) which conforms to eIDAS requirements or other commercial providers such as PDF-Tools.com.

Infrastructure and interfaces needed for deployment

- For a manual deployment by humans standard tools for reading and creating PDF can in many cases be used to deploy and validate 'Image of handwritten signatures' and 'advanced electronic signatures'. Additional signature generating software or service is needed for higher level qualified digital signatures (e.g., the eIDAS compliant ones).

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- To automate the signature (signature of batches in automated workflows) tools providing relevant APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) for deployment of signatures and seals in software must be supplied.
- In addition, both creators and users of signed PDF data need software (human usable and/or API) to provide calculation and/or validation of the hash values of attached data.

Potential cost points – for issuer and customer

- Issuers of signed PDF certificates have to consider expenses for the tools (e.g., PDF viewer) that provide for the creation of signatures and/or licences for software for automated deployment of the signatures. Available products typically sell licences on the basis of a fixed fee per person per year. For simple signatures, some open-source tools can be found.
- In case of advanced and qualified signatures, the issuer also has to consider expenses for obtaining PKI certificates (signature cards) and additional hardware like signature card readers. Again, fees typically are raised per signature PKI certificate per year and buying or renting hardware. If natural persons of an organisation are signers, then one certificate per person must be considered. Tools for advanced signatures are a little cheaper to obtain than qualified signatures.
- On the customer side (i.e., those who receive DCCs), expenses are limited to tools for validation of signatures. Many open access tools (free of charge) are available.

2.2 Signing of “file container”

Principle

The associated signature container (ASiC) is a data container that is used to hold a group of files and digital signatures and/or time assertions that are associated to those objects (ASiC, 2023).

The container is in principle a zip-file which has a specific file extension (for example in Estonia ASICE). The structure of signature data is based on the XML syntax XAdES (XAdES, 2023).

For example, in Estonia the software that is needed to create and open these containers is provided in coordination with the Estonian government (ID, 2023) and together with the fact that every citizen has a mandatory ID-card with digital signing capabilities, leads to nationwide trusted system for digital signing.

Creation of the signed document

- When signing a document the software creates files for metadata and signature files. All files with document to sign are zipped and an ASICE extension is set.
- When creating a signature the application checks if the signer’s certificate is created by an institution/company that is listed in European Union TSP (Trusted Service Providers) list. Also if the certificate is valid for the relevant operation (it has correct validity time; it has the flag that states that the certificate is for creating signatures).

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- While creating the signature, the software also adds a current timestamp to the container. The timestamp is signed using a timestamp provider which also is in the TSP list.

Verifying the signed document

- To verify the signature, the file should be opened in the software that was used to generate the signature.
- To verify the signature, the software uses the signatures and public certificates which are located in the container files.

Security and legal requirements

- Security of the signed documents is according to eIDAS qualified electronic signatures (QES-level) regulation (as in Table 1, type 4).

Advantages

- Multiple files can be used.
- Multiple signatures can be applied.
- Files that the signatures are applied to are not altered. Which leads to the next point – in case evidence arises that the currently used cryptography becomes hackable/breakable then the signed files can be re-signed/re-packaged in new technologies without altering the original files.
- Once set-up, the same infrastructure/services can be used for many different purposes – it isn't DCC or metrology specific solution; no separate cryptographic solutions are needed.

Disadvantages

- Knowledge of this type of signing is not widespread (excluding some countries as Estonia for example), so there is a need to explain to customers how to use the file containers.
- Signing does not work without an internet connection (to service provider).

Infrastructure and interfaces needed for deployment

- Trusted digital cryptographic device linked to a person (for example ID-card, crypto stick, mobile ID) and certificates inside the device are needed.
- Signing of documents with personal signature can be done using publicly available software and personal ID. When using an electronic signature of organisation, it is necessary to create a software environment which enables the use in the organization (user identification, under what conditions the signing/stamping takes place, what is the status of the stamped documents etc.).

Potential cost points

- Issuers of container-based signed certificates have to consider expenses for the tools – physical PKI signature card or crypto stick (HSM, 2023). Even when physical users already have personal tools (e.g., compulsory ID-Card in Estonia, and signing is free for private use) if these are used for professional use, a fee may apply. If a company's

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electronic stamp is used, physical crypto stick costs and typically there will also be a fee for every signature/stamp given.

- A card reader is needed for signature cards.
- Automation of company signing/stamping can be achieved by investing in a software environment, where validated users can apply the company's electronic stamp in a simple "one click" which initiates the signing process in a separately implemented service that runs the signing.
- On the customer side (receiver of signed documents), expenses are limited to tools for opening and validation of signatures. In the case of Estonia for example, the software is free and available in app stores by Microsoft, Google, or Apple.

3 Implementation of DCC signing workflow

While an application of a digital signature to a document such as the DCC is a rather unspectacular process, setting up the infrastructure for signing and maintaining the infrastructure requires input from management and technical support work (in particular working with local IT people). Here is a DCC2GO blueprint for a potential workflow that organisations could use to implement digital signing of DCCs. It comprises three phases in the life-cycle of digital signing and is based on practical workflows and experience from the organisations of the authors.

3.1 Phase 1 – Implementation of signature infrastructure (questions to answer before you can start)

Step 1.1: Planning where to use digital signatures

A digital signature process may not only be introduced exclusively for DCCs but in the best case, the investment should also bring a solution to sign all kinds of documents for an organisation, that need digital signature in the future. Thus, the first step is to bring experts from management, governance, and technical/service divisions together to evaluate what documents should be signed, who is going to sign and how many signatures would be applied per day / month / year. You may find that some signature systems are already in place and consider extension of these to DCCs. Or alternatively, you may find that replacement of the existing systems may be needed in favour of a more universal solution. Even larger organisations are careful with available resources and aim to maintain only one system.

Step 1.2: Evaluation of legal requirements your organization must fulfil

Legal requirements show the boundary conditions under which solutions could be introduced for digital signatures. It starts with the basic question, if policies of the organisation permit digital signatures in business processes. The NMI in Germany found for example that they had to negotiate an update of the organisation's policy with the government to allow digital signatures equally to hand-written signatures. In this respect, your national government may define legal requirements that signatures must be used in your business processes that would also affect DCCs. Similarly, national calibration and or accreditation guidelines may prescribe the use of specific kinds of digital signature. In this step, management, and legal experts, but also some IT experts with relevant background will need to work together to evaluate the relevant legal requirements.

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Step 1.3: Planning of required infrastructure

Having defined the scope of digital signature application and the legal requirements, planning for the technical implementation can start. This will include making decisions on what kind of hardware and software to acquire and how many devices, licences, etc. would be needed. It could also include the requirement to plan for new facilities (rooms) for signing. Some organisations operate a signature server for example in a kind of room that is protected like in a vault. Furthermore, roadmaps are defined for the implementation of the digital signatures including change management, e.g., through pilot services and training of staff. Financial aspects will play an important role when planning the implementation. Not only hardware and software are of interest but also the costs for longer term maintenance of the signing system (see Phase 3 for details). Acceptance by customers will also need to be considered. At this stage not only management and IT experts play an important role, but also the employees who will use the signing system later and who may add technical preferences. For example, some laboratories may already have an automated DCC creation and would benefit from a signature system that allows integration into their software and processes.

Step 1.4: Acquisition and set-up of infrastructure for signing

Following the implementation roadmap, acquisition and set-up of hardware, software and services is done. Depending on the size of the organisation and solution to be implemented, this may take a few months, up to more than a year. All members of your organisation will be involved either in implementing or learning to use the new signature system.

3.2 Phase 2 – Signature in workflow of DCC creation/use (daily business)

Step 2.1: Creation of DCC

DCCs may be created in various ways, from manual information entry to commercial office software and up to fully automated generation using a bespoke software environment. In all cases the structure of the file system has to be determined – including where are files to be signed, where these are moved when signed, and where archived for later use after deploying to customer etc. When planning digital signing of a document, it must be confirmable that it is ready for signing – approval from creator and if specified also from supervisor and that signature is attached to final version of the correct document.

Step 2.2: Application of signatures / seals

If personal signatures are chosen, every person entitled to sign has to have means to do so. If there is no national means available (ID-card with electronic capabilities for example), commercially available solutions have to be implemented. If a signature is put into a file (PDF for example), there has to be the possibility to distinguish the signed files from not signed ones, e.g., by adding some marker to the file name. Container based signing creates a new “container” file with a signed document in it, so it’s easily distinguishable as a signed file. When using organisation signatures/stamps it is necessary to implement a software environment where files can be uploaded, identified and their status indicated (in need of signing, approved, rejected etc.), users are securely identified and can apply correct status to files. The signature of an organisation can then be applied either automatically by an environment or a person entitled to have the rights.

Step 2.3: Storage of signed DCC

When signing with a qualified signature, it gives protection against changing a file's contents but security means against unauthorized erasing or moving the files still needs to be implemented.

Step 2.4: Transmission of signed DCC to customer

The signature gives protection against unintended tampering of information but general confidentiality rules that apply in a organisation have to be applied to be sure that DCC reaches the intended recipient and no other. For extra security there are means available for encrypting the signed files, for example in Estonia a signed file can be encrypted so it can be opened only by a person with specific personal ID number, using ID card or other equivalent electronic identifying means.

Step 2.5: Customer validating (DCC and) signature when receiving DCC (DCC integrity & authenticity checking)

DCC validation is a necessary part of the chosen signing solution. It can be independent software that can check the certificates or customers can validate the signature by means provided by the issuing organisation, e.g., by uploading a file to a website and getting confirmation of authenticity. In the case of signed PDF files, most PDF readers can show details of the signature and origin of signing rights (certificates) associated with a signature. Verification of container based signatures can be done using the same software as for creating and opening the container.

3.3 Phase 3 – Maintenance of signing infrastructure (things to consider for keeping it running)

Step 3.1: Updating hardware and software

The chosen solution must be kept up to date as any other software environment, when physical cards, readers or sticks are used, these might wear and have certificates limited by certain time period.

Step 3.2: Late requests for DCC validation

There has to be a plan how to validate a signature that is given certain amount of time ago, maybe limits for applicable validation time have to be given out. It is essential that signature solution provider has a policy for ageing signatures. General thought has to be given if after longer period of time there would be a possibility to open the files at all. If for example PDF files would not be used anymore, would there still be possibility to open these old files after 10 or 20 years or read and verify the signatures?

Step 3.3: Updating/replacing signatures

Re-signing documents can be needed when cryptographic means used for signing have been updated after previous version is not considered to be safe anymore. For example, in Estonia cryptographic means for signing have been updated several times over years but a solution is been made available for users to re-sign the documents with current level security signatures. The signed document remains thereby unchanged.

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5 Common Abbreviations

ASiC	Associated Signature Container
DCC	Digital Certificate of Calibration
DI	Designated Institute
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
eIDAS	electronic Identification, Authentication and Trust Service
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
NMI	National Metrology Institute
PDF	Portable Document Format
PKI	Public-Private Key Infrastructure
QUE	Qualified Electronic Signature
WORM	Write Once Read Many
XML	eXtensive Markup Language
XadES	XML advances Electronic Signature

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